

REINFORCEMENT MECHANISM IN BAMBOO/EPOXY COMPOSITES

X.J Xian

Institute of Mechanics, Academia Sinica,
Beijing, China.

M.W. Yipp

Department of Applied Biology & Chemical Technology,
Hong Kong Polytechnic, Hong Kong.

F.G. Shin

Department of Applied Physics
Hong Kong Polytechnic, Hong Kong.

ABSTRACT

We have recently developed and evaluated the mechanical properties of bamboo/epoxy composite material. Bamboo mechanically broken down to strands of fibres serves as reinforcement in either unidirectional or bidirectional laminates. An interesting finding is that the laminates have properties generally higher than the corresponding properties of the reinforcing constituent (in this case natural bamboo). This feature differs from most composites fabricated from artificial fibres. In this paper we discuss the mechanisms at work that lead to the enhanced reinforcement. SEM studies confirm that there is a good infiltration of epoxy into the bundles of bamboo fibre, parenchyma and intercellular spaces. Given that this is a cause for enhancement, one way to make better bamboo/epoxy composites would be to infiltrate epoxy into bamboo in a pretreatment before it is moulded. We therefore study the effect of epoxy infiltration in bamboo pretreated by a standard technique used to prepare biological material for histological sectioning, as compared to infiltration by hot-pressing in the course of moulding

bamboo/epoxy laminates. The latter method is found to yield generally better properties.

KEYWORDS: Bamboo; Composites

1. INTRODUCTION

In the evolution of composite materials fabrication, we have seen a change from the use of natural to artificial fibre reinforcements with accompanying development of fabrication technology. The current generation of "advanced" composites have excellent performance, but their incorporation of artificial fibres has increased manufacturing costs, thus limiting wide applications. It is of considerable potential therefore, to seek to develop composite materials based on natural fibres with performance comparable to their artificial counterparts.

A significant weight percentage of bamboo is made up of a variety of elongated cells: the sclerenchyma and vascular bundles. These cells are arranged regularly and orientated along the axis of the bamboo plant, resembling the arrangement of fibres in unidirectionally reinforced composite materials. The bamboo plant itself has been shown to possess high strength, good elasticity and stable performance [1,2]. Previously, we have reported on the effects of fibre size and orientation and resin type on mechanical properties of bamboo reinforced plastics [3,4], but in all cases the bamboo material had not been chemically treated. We have found from our earlier work there has only been limited infiltration of epoxy into and among bamboo fibres, and wonder if better penetration may improve mechanical performance of the product. This paper sets out our investigation on a method of chemical treatment aimed at improving such penetration, the effects of which on the composite allows further understanding of aspects of bamboo reinforcement in bamboo/epoxy composites.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two types of bamboo material were used in this study: Phyllostachys sp. and Bambusoides sp., both of which occur

widely in Asia, and have been shown to be of high mechanical performance [2]. Only the internodal portions of the bamboo was used, and these were cut longitudinally into cylinders of length equal to mould length. The cylinders were cut into strips along their axis, and depending on thickness, each strip was sliced into 3 - 6 layers of approximately 1 - 2 mm thickness. In this way, the longitudinal orientation of the bamboo fibres were retained in the final composite material.

Several different methods of sample preparation were studied to compare the subsequent performance of composites. In the hot press method, the bamboo strips were passed between a pair of steel rollers which separated the woody material into bundles of fibres. These were packed in sheets either unidirectionally [0] or bidirectionally [0/90] in a rectangular mould. Epoxy resin (GY 257) was used as a matrix, with 15% by weight of HY 2958 hardener added. The packed mould was hot-pressed at 100°C and 5 MPa to produce unidirectional and bidirectional laminates. These were then cut into appropriate dimensions for different tests.

In the immersion method, the thin strips of bamboo were directly immersed in epoxy without passing through rollers. One group of specimens were pretreated by first priming the fibres by immersion in 75% ethyl alcohol at 250 Pa pressure for 24 hours, then changing to absolute alcohol, and xylene for 2 hours each. In the latter two changes of immersion liquids, agitation of the containers was provided to improve mixing and penetration. Finally, epoxy was added, with agitation, for another 2 hours, before the hardener was added. This processing schedule is adapted from standard histological techniques and aimed to wet the surfaces of bamboo fibres to enable the epoxy resin to penetrate into the inter- and intra-cellular spaces thereby hoping to reduce separation between the fibres and epoxy-enriched plant matrix particularly under shear stress. When the epoxy began to show signs of curing, the bamboo strips were taken out and curing completed in an oven at 60°C.

To investigate the effect of such pretreatment on the strength of the bamboo itself, a set of bamboo strips were pretreated but not embedded in epoxy. The performance of these strips

could then be compared against untreated strips.

Macroscopic tests were carried out for the large-sized specimens fabricated by the hot-pressing method, on an INSTRON 1195 universal testing machine, while small specimens fabricated by the immersion method were tested on the loading stage of a HITACHI S-570 scanning electron microscope to obtain both mechanical performance data and dynamic fractographic observations.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Mechanical Testing For Bambusoides, composites fabricated by the hot-pressing method had generally better performance than the bamboo itself under tensile, compressive and flexural stresses (Table 1). In fact, it appeared that the tensile and flexural strengths of the unidirectional composite were approximately double the strengths of its reinforcing component. Our data on the unidirectional composite shows a specific strength 3 - 4 times that of mild steel and wood, and parity with ordinary glass fibre-reinforced composites. Bidirectional laminates showed a performance level generally similar to the bamboo itself.

TABLE 1 The mechanical properties of Bambusoides bamboo, epoxy, and bamboo/epoxy composites under macroscopic testing conditions.

Specimen Description	Tension		Compression		Flexure		Short Beam Shear	
	$\bar{\sigma}_t$ (MPa)	E_t (GPa)	$\bar{\sigma}_c$ (MPa)	E_c (GPa)	$\bar{\sigma}_B$ (MPa)	E_B (GPa)	$\bar{\tau}_{13}$ (MPa)	G_{13} (MPa)
Bambusoides bamboo	92-128	11-16	55-79	-	108-226	11	9-11	-
Epoxy	49-78	2-4	-	-	35-60	4	-	-
Bamboo/epoxy; [0]	178-243	45-76	59-129	25-33	208-255	16-25	11-17	610-877
Bamboo/epoxy; [0/90]	98	17	54	-	135	14	-	481

Bambusoides materials prepared by the immersion method were tested microscopically with results shown in Table 2. As in our previous report [4], such testing typically yield lower performance values compared to testing with standard sample sizes. Thus values recorded for untreated bamboo under micro-testing were lower than in Table 1. The composite material showed a reduction in performance of roughly 10% in tensile and compressive strengths and a slight increase under short beam shear test. This is in marked contrast to the data obtained for hot-pressed composites. We have found that most of the performance loss occurred during the pretreatment process, as shown in the data for bamboo which was only processed to the end of the pretreatment stage. Here a loss in performance of roughly 10, 20 and 40% were recorded for tensile, compressive and short beam shear tests compared to untreated bamboo. Subsequent infiltration by epoxy in other samples resulted in a partial redemption in the lost performance, showing that epoxy infiltration is one reinforcement mechanism.

TABLE 2 The mechanical properties of untreated and pretreated bamboo and epoxy-infiltrated Bambusoides composite under microscopic testing conditions.

Specimen Description	Tension σ_t (MPa)	Compression σ_c (MPa)	Short Beam Shear τ_{13} (MPa)
Untreated bamboo	70.6	51.8	13.7
Pretreated bamboo	61.1	40.8	8.5
Bamboo/epoxy	63.0	46.8	14.1

Table 3 shows the performance of specimens of Phyllostachys and its composites, all of which were fabricated by the immersion method without hot-pressing. Under macroscopic tensile testing, the untreated bamboo performed better than the composites which showed a 30% decrease in performance. We have also compared bamboo samples taken from the upper culm with older wood near the base (lower culm) and found the former to be stronger.

TABLE 3 The tensile strength of untreated bamboo and epoxy-infiltrated Phyllostachys composite under macroscopic testing conditions.

Specimen Description	Tension σ_t (MPa)
Upper Culm; untreated	186
Upper Culm; bamboo/epoxy	127
Lower Culm; untreated	125
Lower Culm; bamboo/epoxy	90

Table 4 compares the performance of materials under microtesting, which have been processed to different stages during the fabrication process. The results here are similar to those obtained for Bambusoides, i.e. a significant reduction occurred following pretreatment in alcohol and xylene, which was partially redeemed in the final composite material. The resulting material was still slightly inferior to the untreated bamboo.

TABLE 4 The mechanical properties of untreated and pretreated bamboo, and epoxy-infiltrated Phyllostachys composite under microscopic testing conditions.

Specimen Description	Tension σ_t (MPa)	Compression σ_c (MPa)	Short Beam Shear τ_{13} (MPa)
Untreated bamboo	80.1	57.4	17.1
Pretreated bamboo	73.4	41.6	12.4
Bamboo/epoxy	78.5	54.0	15.7

3.2 Discussion of the Reinforcing Mechanism in Bamboo/epoxy Composites

For artificial fibre-reinforced composites, the tensile strength (σ_t) of the fibre is around ten times that of the matrix, and the resulting composite has a σ_t value which is a third to half of the fibre. Carbon fibre, for example, has a tensile strength 50 times that of epoxy, yet the σ_t of unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite is only about half that of carbon fibre. In the case of the bamboo-epoxy system, the tensile σ_t of bamboo is around twice that of epoxy. The tensile σ_t of the unidirectional bamboo/epoxy specimens is approximately twice that of bamboo. The same is true of its flexural properties. As such behaviour is anomalous among fibre-reinforced composites, it is worthwhile to study the mechanisms which lead to such unexpected enhancement.

A comparison between untreated bamboo, and pretreated bamboo/epoxy composite (fabricated without hot-pressing) is shown in Figures 1a and b, where it can be seen that chemical pretreatment enhanced the entry of the resin into the lumina of and around the fibres, as compared to hot-pressed specimens which have been reported in [4]. The intrusion of epoxy into the fibre lumina increases the load bearing cross sectional

FIGURE 1 Cross sections of (a) untreated bamboo and (b) bamboo/epoxy fabricated by the immersion method, showing good infiltration of epoxy.

area increased the composite's capability to sustain and transfer load. However, a significant amount of deformation and damage of the fibre cell wall is apparent in Figure 2, where the bamboo strip was only subjected to pretreatment. Such damages sustained during pretreatment lowers the mechanical performance of the resultant composite material, as indeed we have shown in Tables 1 and 2.

FIGURE 2 Longitudinal surface of bamboo fibres after pretreatment, showing damage and deformation of cell wall.

Bamboo cellulose is built up from $C_6H_{10}O_5$ monomers. These are kept together in the first plane by numerous and strong hydrogen bonds, in the second plane by much weaker Van der Waals forces, and in the third plane by covalent bonds. After hot-pressing, plastic deformation occurs, thus improving interface bonding. Furthermore, the application of pressure increases the fibre density of the resultant composite, thereby increasing both strength and stiffness. Both these effects are apparent in Figure 3. Specimens which had been processed without hot-pressing are therefore disadvantaged in having lower fibre density, and are therefore comparatively inferior under mechanical testing.

FIGURE 3 Bamboo/epoxy fabricated by hot pressing, showing compression of rounded cross sectional areas into polygons with improved interfacial contact.

4. CONCLUSION

Using a traditional hot-pressing method for the fabrication of bamboo/epoxy composites, we have found that the tensile and flexural strengths of the unidirectional composite amounted to twice that of the reinforcing component. This is different from the characteristics of composites reinforced by artificial fibres. Scanning electron microscopy confirmed that there is a good infiltration of the epoxy resin between the reinforcing fibres. We have thus attempted to induce improved resin penetration through a chemical pretreatment process with the aim of improving the performance of the composite even further. Although improved penetration had been achieved, we have found a decrease in load bearing capability using this pretreatment method. SEM studies showed a considerable amount of damage to the bamboo fibres resulting from pretreatment, which accounted for the significant weakening of pretreated bamboo compared to untreated bamboo. However, subsequent inter- and intra-cellular infiltration with epoxy did compensate for the weakening, showing that efficient infiltration and bonding are significant factors which increased the overall strength of bamboo/epoxy materials. It should be noted that in the immersion method, no hot-pressing was included during fabrication.

Our findings with hot-pressed materials showed that fibre density was greatly increased during this process, leading to increasing load-bearing capabilities. This density increase is possible in bamboo fibres, since the fibres are essentially dead cells with an empty lumen in the centre, which is highly amenable to compression. This is not true for artificial fibres which are solid inside. Thus hot-pressing improves the performance of the composite by increasing fibre density compared to natural bamboo and also compresses the rounded cross-sectional areas of bamboo fibres into closely applied angular surfaces, thereby increasing interface bonding. On the other hand, intracellular penetration of the resin also increases bonding strength. These are the possible mechanisms which may account for the resultant improvement in mechanical performance of the composite compared to its component materials.

5. REFERENCES

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